

DIFFERENSIAL TENGLAMALARNI EYLER USULIDA YECHISH VA UNI AMALIY MATEMATIK DASTURIY PAKETLAR YORDAMIDA MODELLASHTIRISH

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu ishda differensial tenglamalarni sonli yechish usullaridan biri bo'lgan Eyer va Runge–Kutta usullari o'rganildi. Differensial tenglamalarning nazariy asoslari, sonli yechim olish prinsiplari hamda amaliy matematik dasturiy paketlarda qo'llanishi yoritildi. Hisoblash jarayonlari Excel, Matlab va Mathcad dasturida bajarilib, maxsus funksiyalar yordamida taqribiy yechimlar olindi. Olingan natijalar sonli usullarning aniqligi va amaliy ahamiyatini ko'rsatib berdi. Shuningdek, usullarning muhandislik, fizika va matematik modellashtirishdagi qo'llanilish imkoniyatlari tahlil qilindi.

Kalit so'zlar: Differensial tenglama, Eyer usuli, Runge–Kutta usuli, sonli usullar, taqribiy yechim, hisoblash matematikasi, algoritm, qadam uzunligi, matematik modellashtirish, Mathcad, sonli hisoblash, boshlang'ich shart, differensial hisob.

Abstract. This work studies the Euler and Runge–Kutta methods, which are one of the methods for numerically solving differential equations. The theoretical foundations of differential equations, the principles of obtaining numerical solutions, and their application in practical mathematical software packages are covered. The calculation processes were performed in Excel, Matlab, and Mathcad, and approximate solutions were obtained using special functions. The results obtained showed the accuracy and practical significance of numerical methods. The possibilities of using the methods in engineering, physics, and mathematical modeling were also analyzed.

Keywords: Differential equation, Euler method, Runge–Kutta method, numerical methods, approximate solution, computational mathematics, algorithm, step length, mathematical modeling, Mathcad, numerical calculation, initial condition, differential calculus.

Eyer usuli XVIII asrda mashhur shveysariyalik matematik Leonhard Euler tomonidan ishlab chiqilgan. U differensial tenglamalarni sonli usulda yechish g'oyasini birinchi bo'lib ilmiy asosda taklif qilgan olimlardan biridir.

XVIII asrda ko'plab fizik, astronomik va mexanik masalalarni analitik usulda yechish qiyin bo'lgan. Shu sababli matematiklar taqribiy hisoblash usullarini yaratishga ehtiyoj sezishgan. Eyer differensial tenglamaning yechimini kichik qadamlar orqali ketma-ket hisoblash mumkinligini ko'rsatdi.

Uning asosiy g'oyasi funksiyaning hosilasidan foydalanib keyingi nuqtadagi qiymatni taxminiy aniqlashdan iborat edi. Keyinchalik bu yondashuv “Eyer usuli” deb nomlandi.

Leonhard Euler (1707–1783) matematika tarixidagi eng buyuk olimlardan biri hisoblanadi. U: differensial tenglamalar, matematik analiz, mexanika, sonlar nazariyasi, fizika sohalariga katta hissa qo'shgan.

Eyler usuli keyinchalik boshqa olimlar tomonidan takomillashtirildi. Natijada: takomillashgan Eyler usuli, Runge–Kutta usullari, Adams usullari kabi aniqroq sonli usullar yaratildi. Hozirgi kunda Eyler usuli: matematika, fizika, muhandislik, iqtisodiyot, kompyuter modellashtirish sohalarida boshlang'ich sonli usul sifatida keng qo'llaniladi.¹

Quyidagi.

$$y' = x + \cos\left(\frac{y}{\sqrt{5}}\right)$$

birinchi tartibli differentsial tenglamaning

$$x_0=1.8 \quad y_0=2.6$$

boshlang'ich shartni qanoatlantiruvchi [1.8, 2.8] oraliqda yechimini $h=0.1$ qadami bilan, $e=0.001$ aniqlikda

Yechish.

1. Berilgan differentsial tenglamani Eyler usulida yechamiz.

Buning uchun [1.8, 2.8] oraliqni

$$n = \frac{b-a}{h} = \frac{2.8-1.8}{0.1} = 10$$

ya'ni, $n=10$ ta bo'lakka ajratamiz. Bo'linish nuqtalarini:

$$x_i = x_{i-1} + h, \quad i=1, 2, \dots, 10$$

formulaga asosan topamiz.

$$x_1 = x_0 + h = 1.8 + 0.1 = 1.9$$

$$x_2 = x_1 + h = 1.9 + 0.1 = 2.0$$

shuningdek

$$x_3=2.1, x_4=2.2, x_5=2.3, x_6=2.4, x_7=2.5, x_8=2.6, x_9=2.7, x_{10}=2.8$$

Berilgan tenglamaning o'ng tomonidagi

$$F(x; y) = x + \cos\left(\frac{y}{\sqrt{5}}\right)$$

funktsiyaga asosan, Eyler qoidasi bilan quyidagi

$$y_{i+1} = y_i + h f(x_i; y_i), \quad i=1, 2, \dots, 10$$

formulaga asosan berilgan differentsial tenglama yechimining qiymatlarini quyidagicha topamiz.

$$\begin{aligned} y_1 &= y_0 + h f(x_0, y_0) = y_0 + h (x_0 + \cos(y_0/\sqrt{5})) = \\ &= 2.6 + 0.1(1.8 + \cos(2.6/\sqrt{5})) = 2.6 + 0.1(1.8 + 0.3968) = 2.81968 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} y_2 &= y_1 + h f(x_1, y_1) = y_1 + h (x_1 + \cos(y_1/\sqrt{5})) = \\ &= 2.819 + \end{aligned}$$

$$0.1(1.9 + \cos(2.819/\sqrt{5})) = 2.819 + 0.1(1.9 + 0.3968) = 3.03948$$

SHuningdek, quyidagilarni topamiz:

$$y_3=3.261, y_4=3.4831, y_5=3.7045, y_6=3.926$$

$$y_7=4.1478, y_8=4.3701, y_9=4.5931, y_{10}=4.8173$$

Eyler usuli algoritmi EXCEL dasturida juda soda bajariladi. Uning ishchi formulasi $y_{i+1} = y_i + h f(x_i; y_i)$, $i=1, 2, \dots, n$ dan iborat. Jadvalga n , $[a, b]$, x_0 , y_0 va x_i larning qiymatini joylashtirib y_{i+1} qiymatini hisoblash formulasini berish kifoya. Bunda $h=(b-a)/n$ ni aniqlab $x_{i+1} = x_i + h$ formula orqali x_1, x_2 va x_n lar qiymati hisoblab yoziladi. EXCEL jadval orqali hisoblashlar bajarilganda berilgan $[a, b]$, x_0 larni o'zgartirilishi bilan, x_1, x_2 va x_n lar

¹ Boyzoqov A., Qayumov SH. Hisoblash matematikasi asoslari. Toshkent, TDIU, 2000.

avtomatik o'zgarishiga e'tibor qaratish kerak. Shunda berilgan tenglamani har xil oraliklarda turli boshlang'ich qiymat uchun avtomatik yechim olinadigan jadval yaratiladi. Quyida shunday jadval formulasi va turli boshlang'ich shart bilan olingan yechim berilgan. ²

	A	B	C	D
1	Quyidagi Koshi mas			
2				
3	$y' = \frac{y}{x} - y^2$		$y_0(1) = 1,0$	
4				
5	YECHISH: Eyler usulidan foydalanamiz			
6			$y_{i+1} = y_i + hf(x_i; y_i)$	
7	a=x0= 1		y0= 1	
8	b= 2			
9	n= 10			
10	h= =(B8-B7)/B9			
11				
12	xi	yi		
13	=B7	=D7		
14	=A13+h	=B13+h*(B13/A13-A13^2)		
15	=A14+h	=B14+h*(B14/A14-A14^2)		
16	=A15+h	=B15+h*(B15/A15-A15^2)		
17	=A16+h	=B16+h*(B16/A16-A16^2)		
18	=A17+h	=B17+h*(B17/A17-A17^2)		
19	=A18+h	=B18+h*(B18/A18-A18^2)		
20	=A19+h	=B19+h*(B19/A19-A19^2)		
21	=A20+h	=B20+h*(B20/A20-A20^2)		
22	=A21+h	=B21+h*(B21/A21-A21^2)		
23	=A22+h	=B22+h*(B22/A22-A22^2)		

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G
1	Quyidagi Koshi masalasini yeching.						
2							
3	$y' = \frac{y}{x} - y^2$		$y_0(1) = 1,0$		$x \in [1,0; 2,0]$		
4							
5	YECHISH: Eyler usulidan foydalanamiz						
6			$y_{i+1} = y_i + hf(x_i; y_i)$		$i = 1, 2, \dots, 10$		
7	a=x0= 1		y0= 1				
8	b= 2						
9	n= 10						
10	h= 0,1						
11							
12	xi	yi					
13	1	1					
14	1,1	1					
15	1,2	0,97					
16	1,3	0,907					
17	1,4	0,807					
18	1,5	0,669					
19	1,6	0,489					
20	1,7	0,263					
21	1,8	-0,01					
22	1,9	-0,335					
23	2	-0,713					

Differentsial tenglamalarni Yechish funksiyasi– dsolve

Bu funktsiya bilan oddiy differentsial tenglama va tenglamalar tizimi uchun Koshi masalasini analitik Yechish mumkin. U quyidagi shaklda yoziladi:

- dsolve('tenglama1', 'tenglama2', ...)

'tenglama1', 'tenglama2', ... teng belgisi bilan yozilgan tenglamalar va bo'shlang'ich shartlardir(tenglamalar oldin yoziladi, bo'shlang'ich shartlar keyin yoziladi.

Bu tenglamalarda o'zgaruvchi ko'rsatilmasa uni vaqt- t deb oladi. Boshqa o'zgaruvchiga nisbatan ko'rilsa , argumentlar ro'yxatining o'xiriga o'zaruvchi nomini kiritib qo'yish kerak. D xarfi erkin o'zgaruvchi bo'yicha xosilani bildiradi, shuning uchun erkin o'zgaruvchi nomi D xarfdan boshlanmasligi kerak. D2 ikkinchi tartibli xosilani bildiradi, D3 uchinchi tartibli xosilani bildiradi va x.k.

Boshlang'ich shartlar ham tenglik bilan beriladi, masalan. 'y(a)=b' или 'Dy(a)=b'.

Agar boshlang'ich shartlar soni tenglamalar sonidan kam bo'lsa, yechim C1,C2, ... ixtiyoriy konstantalarga bog'liq holda chiqadi. Analitik yechimning biror nuqtadagi qiymatini topish sarur bo'lsa t o'zgaruvchiga qiymat berib subs(y,t) funksiyasi orqali o'rniga qo'yish bilan hisoblaymiz.

Misol. $dy/dt=t-2y$ differensial tenglamani, $y(0)=1$ chart bo'yich analitik yechimi va uning [0,1] oralikdagi qiymatlari quyidagicha aniqlanadi

² N.K.Sayidova “Sonli usullar va dasturlash”. O‘quv qo‘llanma. “Omadbek print number one”, 2023 Andijon.

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C:\MATLAB6p5\work\MutalibDiff0.m
Edit View Text Debug Breakpoints Web W
1 - y=dsolve('Dy=t-2*y','Y(0)=1')
2 - t=0.04:0.1:1;
3 - y=subs(y,t);
4 - [t;y]'

Command Window
>>
y =
1/2*t-1/4+5/4*exp(-2*t)
ans =
0.0400    0.9239
0.1400    0.7647
0.2400    0.6435
0.3400    0.5533
0.4400    0.4885
0.5400    0.4445
0.6400    0.4175
0.7400    0.4045
0.8400    0.4030
0.9400    0.4107
    
```

1-rasm.Differensial tenglamani Yechishda dsolve funksiyasi

Endi Eyley usuli va Runge-Kutta usullari tavsifini va u bilan berilgan differentsial tenglamaning taqribiy yechimini topishni MathCad amaliy matematik paketida ko'ramiz.

Misol.

$$y + \sqrt{xy} = xy';$$

$f(x, y) := \frac{y + \sqrt{x \cdot y}}{x}$

$RK(x_0, y_0, h, n) :=$

```

x0 ← x0
y0 ← y0
for i ∈ 0..n-1
    k1 ← f(x_i, y_i)
    k2 ← f(x_i + h/2, y_i + h/2 * k1)
    k3 ← f(x_i + h/2, y_i + h/2 * k2)
    k4 ← f(x_i + h, y_i + h * k3)
    y_{i+1} ← y_i + h/6 * (k1 + 2 * k2 + 2 * k3 + k4)
    x_{i+1} ← x_i + h
augment(x, y)
        
```

Mathcad'da maxsus funksiya yaratganmiz. Undagi k1, k2, k3, k4 koeffitsientlari har bir qadamda funksiya qiymatini 4 xil nuqtada tekshiradi. Bu usulga juda yuqori aniqlik beradi.

Hisoblash shartlari:

$Result := RK(1, 1, 0.1, 20)$ RK(1, 1, 0.1, 20): (1, 1) — Boshlang'ich nuqta(x=1,y=1)

0.1 — Qadam uzunligi (h).

20 — Qadamlar soni.

Result =	<table border="1" style="border-collapse: collapse;"> <tr><td>1</td><td>1</td></tr> <tr><td>1.1</td><td>1.207</td></tr> <tr><td>1.2</td><td>1.429</td></tr> <tr><td>1.3</td><td>1.663</td></tr> <tr><td>1.4</td><td>1.911</td></tr> <tr><td>1.5</td><td>2.17</td></tr> <tr><td>1.6</td><td>2.44</td></tr> <tr><td>1.7</td><td>2.722</td></tr> <tr><td>1.8</td><td>3.013</td></tr> <tr><td>1.9</td><td>3.315</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>3.627</td></tr> <tr><td>2.1</td><td>3.947</td></tr> <tr><td>2.2</td><td>4.277</td></tr> <tr><td>2.3</td><td>4.615</td></tr> <tr><td>2.4</td><td>4.961</td></tr> <tr><td>2.5</td><td>5.315</td></tr> <tr><td>2.6</td><td>5.678</td></tr> <tr><td>2.7</td><td>6.048</td></tr> <tr><td>2.8</td><td>6.425</td></tr> <tr><td>2.9</td><td>6.81</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>7.201</td></tr> </table>	1	1	1.1	1.207	1.2	1.429	1.3	1.663	1.4	1.911	1.5	2.17	1.6	2.44	1.7	2.722	1.8	3.013	1.9	3.315	2	3.627	2.1	3.947	2.2	4.277	2.3	4.615	2.4	4.961	2.5	5.315	2.6	5.678	2.7	6.048	2.8	6.425	2.9	6.81	3	7.201
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Ushbu misolda differensial tenglama Mathcad dasturida Runge–Kutta usuli yordamida sonli yechildi. Hisoblash jarayonida boshlang‘ich nuqta ($x_0=1$, $y_0=1$) qadam uzunligi $h=0.1$ va qadamlar soni $n=20$ qilib olindi. Dasturda maxsus RK funksiyasi tuzilib, k_1 , k_2 , k_3 , k_4 koeffitsiyentlari orqali har bir qadamdagi qiymatlar aniq hisoblandi.

Natijalar shuni ko‘rsatdiki, Runge–Kutta usuli differensial tenglamalarni yechishda yuqori aniqlik beradi va hisoblash jarayonini soddalashtiradi. Ayniqsa, Mathcad muhiti formulalarni qulay kiritish, jadval va grafiklarni avtomatik hosil qilish imkoniyati bilan amaliy masalalarni samarali yechishga yordam beradi.

Shuningdek, ushbu usul muhandislik, fizika, texnika va matematik modellashtirish masalalarida keng qo‘llanilishi sababli muhim sonli usullardan biri hisoblanadi.

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